

EBFMC25-OP-86 · One-Year Evaluation of Adult Immunization Unit: Patient Profiles and Vaccination Data

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The low immunization rates among adults in Turkey contribute to the increased prevalence of vaccine-preventable diseases (Karaoğlu, Taş, & Toprak, 2022). The growing elderly population and the rising prevalence of chronic diseases make it imperative to expand adult immunization services. In this study, the one-year data of the adult immunization unit established in a tertiary hospital were analyzed to examine patient demographics, the distribution of chronic diseases, and the characteristics of the administered vaccines.

Materials and Methods: In this cross-sectional descriptive study, electronic records of patients who applied to the adult immunization unit within the family medicine clinic in 2024 were retrospectively reviewed. Age, gender, chronic diseases, administered vaccines (type and dose), number of visits, and consultation data were analyzed.

Results: A total of 274,653 short message invitations were sent to individuals who were either 65 years or older or aged 18-64 with a disease that required immunization. A total of 2,445 unique patients responded to the invitation, resulting in 2,741 visits. Immunization counseling was provided in all visits. Of the patients, 72.6% (n=1,776) were male, and 79.8% (n=1,952) were aged 65 and above. The most common chronic diseases were diabetes mellitus (n=379), chronic heart disease (n=169), and chronic kidney failure (n=117). A total of 2,232 doses of vaccines were administered. Among these, the most frequently administered vaccines were conjugate pneumococcal with 975 doses (43.7%), tetanus with 644 doses (28.8%), seasonal influenza with 448 doses (20.1%), and hepatitis B with 156 doses (7.0%).

Conclusion: The majority of patients applying to the adult immunization unit were male and over 65 years old. Diabetes mellitus was the most prominent chronic disease. Pneumococcal and tetanus vaccines were the most frequently administered vaccines. These findings emphasize the importance of targeting risk groups in adult immunization programs.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Adult immunization, chronic disease, pneumococcal vaccine, tetanus vaccine

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Karaođlu, S. A., Taş, B. G., & Toprak, D. (2022). Adult vaccine-related knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors in Turkey. *Clinical and Experimental Vaccine Research*, 11(2), 133–140.

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